

HOW TO IMPROVE CLT METHOD VIA THE APPS

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Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is an approach to the teaching of second and foreign languages that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language. It is also referred to as "Communicative Approach". Understanding the importance of CLT method, our research aims at verifying the effects of "the application of using CLT method in English 10 to improve students' speaking skills" as well as confirming that to what extent it can affect the student's motivation along with the success of the teachers and the lesson progress. A survey was conducted among 43 students of class 10A1 in Luong The Vinh high school by having them do questionnaire papers consisted of 10 questions. Simultaneously, to assess their speaking skills, we also have them do speaking test with 6 marking criteria. The results indicated that students got higher marks in the second speaking test and they were all involved in speaking during the lesson with CLT method. Apparently, students' speaking skills can be improved with CLT method.

In the globalization era, having ability to speak English is considered a springboard for getting well-paid jobs and promotion prospects. Thus, thousands of people around the world have been flocking to learn English, with a view to communicating with one another. In fact, speaking is a productive skill, so it is regarded as a paramount part to communicate effectively. Teachers, however, find it hard to teach, and there is a variety of reasons leading to the fact that numerous students often feel a great deal of anxiety for speaking English. Knowing the importance of speaking in learning a language and difficulties students usually face when speaking, a large number of researches have been conducted to find an effective methodology in teaching speaking. It has come to our knowledge that CLT method has been allegedly a good choice for ESL (English as a second language) teachers worldwide to employ in their classrooms.

CLT emerged as a new teaching method in Britain in the 1970s. That method can be understood as a set of principles about the goals of language teaching, how learners learn a language, the kinds of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and the roles of teachers and learners in the classroom (Richards, 2006). In recent years, there have been a lot of studies on CLT method concerned with speaking skills. For instance, study done with games applied to teach students speaking (Fujioka, 1998), communicative activities to promote speaking in a second language (Kayi, 2006). In addition, Nguyen Minh Hue (2010) proposed some techniques to encourage reluctant ESL learners to speak in the classroom, Efrizal (2012) suggested some communicative activities to improve students' speaking. Efrizal (2012) also indicated that CLT method is of ones can be applied to teaching speaking and improve students' speaking achievement.

Most researchers above generally acknowledge that CLT method is a reliable way to have learners to get the goal of learning a language. In Vietnam-learning situation, however, more studies need to be carried out to determine the effects of CLT method in teaching speaking. That is the reason why we conduct this research. The purpose of the research reported here was an attempt to ascertain the effects of using CLT method and to determine whether CLT method can be used to improve students' speaking skills. Accordingly, we ourselves can get a

wide knowledge of CLT method, create applicably communicative activities to teach speaking, and get experience to develop the teaching speaking skills.

We originally assumed that speaking skills in learning a language is more important than any other ones and taking advantage of CLT method probably produces new English speakers. Now many linguistics and ESL teachers agree on that students learn to speak in the second language by “interacting”. CLT approach serves best for this aim. We should know that it is necessary for us to apply CLT method on effectively speaking development.

One conclusion is that teacher training programs should include the use of the CLT method in teaching English. The results could lead us to conclude that Vietnamese students can speak English as well as a native speakers. Students consequently often evaluate their success in learning as well as the effectiveness of their English class on the basis of how well they feel they have improved in their spoken proficiency. The relevant feedback from the participants in interview is the treatment for the researcher and teachers to provide strategic implementation in the ESL class, to know the progress in what degrees and to understand the problem remarkably. It is important to learn speaking because speaking is a primary mode of communication and a person who has the ability to speak well would be able to communicate effectively with others. Accordingly, we make sure that theory about the roles of CLT method can improve student level in speaking skills.

Our study is unlikely to produce concrete results of the applying CLT method to teach speaking. If we have more time and get a great number of students from different high schools in Ho Chi Minh city to take part in our reasearch; accordingly, this report could be more reliable and concinving. Correspondingly, there is a need to do a large-scale research on CLT method with its various sides. In other words, we should have more studies on demonstrating the outcome of applying CLT method to teach speaking, writing, grammar, etc.

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